

Impact Of Employee Commitment As A Tool For Enhancing Productivity In The Management Of School Service Delivery In Public Senior Secondary School In Obio Akpor Local Government Area Of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated impact of employee commitment as a tool for enhancing productivity in management of school service delivery in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of River State. The purpose of the study was to examine the ways employees' commitment as a tool enhance productivity in management of school service delivery. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population was 1,250 teachers in 20 public senior secondary schools in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The sample size was 375 teachers using simple random sampling technique which represents 30% percent of the population. A validated questionnaire titled Impact of Employee Commitment as a Tool for Enhancing Productivity in the Management of School Service Delivery in Public Senior Secondary School Questionnaire (IECTEMSSDQ) was used for data collection. The reliability co-efficient of 0.88 was obtained using Cronbach alpha. A modified Likerts scale of four points scale was used. Mean, SD and rank order statistics were used to answered research question while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 of significance. The criterion mean of 2.50 accepted and below 2.50 was rejected. The result revealed that school leadership, delegation of authority and responsibility amongst others boost employee commitment level at workplace. It was concluded that the level of success recorded in the educational system is attributed to employee level of commitment. It was recommended that the ministry of education, as a matter of urgency should promote teachers as at when due, this will increase their commitment levels, and also involve teachers in decision making process. This will, as well, make teachers feel that the organization they belong recognizes them.

Keywords: Employee Commitments, Management, Secondary schools, Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary secondary schools, where the quality of education is paramount, the role of committed employees to this effect cannot be overstated. Employee commitment, often defined as individual's emotional and cognitive attachment to organization, has been shown to significantly influence productivity and performance. This review examines the literature of employee commitment and its impact on productivity within the context of secondary schools.

The primary objective of education is to transmit the norms, values, and acceptable knowledge to the learners to fit in adequately for the world of work. However, this laudable objective cannot be achieved if teachers are not committed with their assigned task. This is so because anything you give a casual approach will diminish and will not produce results. Employee commitment is an important factor in the success of any school. School with high levels of employee commitment are more likely to be motivated and engaged which can lead to improved students learning outcome. School as an institution of learning is primarily designed to nurture and inculcate skills and knowledge to the learners for a long useful life. This is because the goal of every school is to enable their students develop intellectual skills, which is an essential ingredient to fit into the society adequately and make life more fulfilling. To this end it is pertinent to state that the impact employee commitment remains a viable mean to drive innovation and productivity among teachers, thereby contributing to a more dynamic and responsive school system. Employees improve academic outcome, and commitment is cardinal to the development of any society and thus school systems can create opportunities for leadership skill development through mentor programs and learning projects design to impart competitive skills. Teachers will equip students with long useful skills for sustainable development. An employee can only perform excellently when he has zero tolerance for his none-performance. This implies that employee commitment at workplace is built on teachers having that resilience spirit or zeal to put to practice his energy and skills to work to ensure an organizations aims and objectives are accomplished. It is imperative to state categorically that the school as an enlightened organization is seriously in need of committed individuals to foster qualitative education for healthy society.

Effective management of school requires the services of committed employee . When employee are committed with their job function it increases their competency level. This is so because teachers knowledge factor and commitment level shape the direction of students, and play a crucial roles in moulding, and building life long skills in students to fit in adequately for societal needs and contribute meaningfully to the growth and development of the state. Ultimately, committed employees are more likely to provide high-quality education, improve student outcomes, and contribute to the overall success of Nigerian secondary schools.

In the context of secondary education, committed employees, such as teachers and administrators, are more likely to exhibit higher levels of job satisfaction, lower turnover rates, and improved performance. Secondary school education, a pivotal stage in a student's academic journey, aims to prepare them for higher education, vocational training, and adult life. The concept of secondary education has evolved significantly over time, reflecting societal changes and educational philosophies Miskel, (2011) found that committed employee create a more positive and collaborative school environment. This in no doubt fosters better relationships between staff, students and parents leading to improved communication, respect for organizational well-being. Similarly, Fullan, (2007) stated that committed employee are eager to learn and grow, actively participating in professional development opportunities. This fosters a culture of continuous improvement and innovation, leading to more effective teaching practices and curriculum for healthy school functioning.

Statement of the problem.

Teachers constitute a significant input of any educational system in the world, because they are critical instrument in transmission of knowledge to learners. Therefore, their commitment level determine to a great extent the quality of teaching and learning outcome. Studies abound where many teachers give a casual approach in the various area of their statutory function. The most concerning aspect as a result of this is reckless attitude of teachers is in the increasing rate which reflect in learners low performance in

school. In the light of this background this study investigated impact of employee commitment as a tool for enhancing productivity in the management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government of Rivers State.

Aims and objectives of the study

The aim of this study was to examine the impact of employee commitment as a tool for enhancing productivity in the management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. Investigate the ways can employee commitment as a tool for enhancing productivity in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. Examine the ways delegation of authority and responsibility enhanced productivity in the management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What are the ways to use employee commitment as a management tool for for enhancing service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.?
2. What are the ways delegation of authority and responsibility by principal enhanced teachers commitment in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the study;

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the ways employee commitment as a management tool school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female on the ways delegation of authority and responsibility by principal enhanced teachers commitment in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Concept definition

The word employee commitment invites various response from different scholar's. Employee commitment from what ever perspective involves total compliance to an assigned task. In this era, nothing happens through sheer chance, there must be rational decisions and objectives to be pursued. Employee commitment is the willingness of teachers to respect the values, norms and readiness to participate in the affairs of organization with the intention of facilitating accomplishment of desired objectives. It is also regarded as the consciousness of a teachers to fully bring in his/ her strength, skills, and knowledge, even resources in pursuit of organizational set goals. Conceptualizing employee commitment, CAMBRIDGE English dictionary as cited in Ibiyeomie, (2012) define employee commitment as the willingness to give your times and and energy to something. He stressed further that life without commitment will end in frustration. Anywhere you see results, is a reflection somebody was committed doing something. Teacher's constitute a significant input in realization of qualitative education delivery, because in preparation (job commitment) there is greatness. Employee commitment is a major tool for enhancing productivity in management of school. In the context of the school system, employee commitment connotes the dedication, unwavering zeal, and enthusiasm the teachers, school administrators, and others staff member display towards their assigned tasked. Research evidence has proven that a strong sence of commitment among school employees can be a powerful tool for enhancing productivity and overall school success. in a related development, studies by Hattic, (2009) found that teachers commitment level in school had a moderate effect size of students achievement. Korman (2008), stated that commitment is an attitude about employee's loyalty towards organization and its continuous that shows itself by how individual participation in organizational decisions paying attention to members and organization welfare.

Factually, there is nothing extraordinary on its own, it is the teachers input with commitment that makes it different from others at workplace. Literally, it is a non-disputable fact that many employees go to their various work place for mere leisure, rather than being committed for the job they were employed and paid for; this act of negligence has been identified as a misplace of priority and unhealthy phenomenon for education system. Committed employees are critical thinkers, they develop strategies on how to move the organization they belong to forward, and as well better the organization the way they meet it, owing to the fact that when the organization succeeds, they are as well succeeded. Objectively, it is normal for an employee to spell out what he/her tends to achieve in the course of discharging their statutory functions, this is because dedicated teachers foster quality education delivery, and as well increase students' academic performance for competitive advantage.

The mindset the teachers have for his job determines to a large extent how productive it will be. This is because the mindset of a teacher towards his job controls the outward nature of his job. According to Proverbs (22:29) 'Seest thou a man diligent in his work, he shall stand before kings; he shall not stand before mean men.' This signifies that it pays to be productive, because it gives one edge over another. Committed employees help to promote knowledge which creates a sustainable future for the youths and as well equip students with skills for sustainable development. It is believed that development of students in terms of quality is reliant on how committed and competent teachers are, and their ability to impact same in learners. Factually, delegation of authority and responsibility by a principal gives subordinates a cutting edge to develop their skills. It is a well-known fact that every employee feels excited when the superordinate delegates duties to act on their behalf, they tend to work harder because they feel their presence is recognized. The need to delegate functions to subordinates by the superordinate has become a modern way of school management. This is because people die, retire, and as well resign with their current job, it is the knowledge and skills acquired by subordinates through their superordinate that keeps the hope alive for such organization. This helps save cost for organization to hire an expert to replace such position immediately. Delegation of authority and responsibility from principals to teachers has been a subject of extensive research in educational administration. This practice is recognized as a powerful tool for enhancing teacher commitment, job satisfaction, and overall school performance. According to motivation theories by Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, delegation can fulfill higher-order needs like esteem and self-actualization, as it empowers teachers and recognizes their capabilities. Also, Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory: Delegation can influence both hygiene factors (e.g., job security, salary) and motivators (e.g., achievement, recognition), leading to increased job satisfaction and commitment. Vroom's in his Expectancy theory maintains that by delegating authority, principals can increase teachers' expectancy that their efforts will lead to good performance, which in turn will lead to valued rewards, thus boosting motivation.

However, numerous studies have demonstrated the positive impact of delegation on teacher commitment. In the words of Tschannen-Moran (2014), Trust is a critical factor in successful delegation. When principals trust teachers with decision-making authority, it fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility, leading to increased commitment. Similarly, Gronn (2002), maintains that effective delegation involves transferring decision-making responsibilities based on teachers' skills and expertise. This empowers teachers, enhances their job satisfaction, and ultimately boosts their commitment. Also, Akumah (2008), asserts that Delegation of supervisory and advisory functions to departmental heads can lead to better school management and increased teacher commitment. In a related development Lee and Kim (2021), affirms that Principals should delegate tasks based on teachers' capabilities and expertise. This can lead to increased teacher autonomy, job satisfaction, and commitment. Admittedly, many teachers have lost confidence in their job function because of what they considered as an unfair treatment, such as delay in promotion, training program amongst others. Teachers' experience did not significantly affect their performance, the fact still remains that there is need to promote them as at when due, enrich them intellectually to increase their commitment level for the benefit of the school. In the same vein, Lee et al (2013), found that employee commitment will increase at work place when they feel affiliation with the organization, and also when organization recognizes them as part of the organization. This will increase

their productivity and the commitment level. They stressed further that it is necessary for every organization to have outstanding performance on long time basis. In the word of Mkpa (2005), organization such as school system needs employee who are capable of demonstrating the highest quality of professional competence in all criteria for efficiency and effectiveness in service delivery. He further stressed that employee should demonstrate qualities such as innovativeness such that the employees receptive to always exploring and applying new idea on new subject competences in demonstration of appropriate teaching skills to cater for variety of learners interest, and moral delivery in terms of relationship with learners such that the employees does not take undue advantage over them. Ultimately, what makes employees leave or stay in an organisation differs. The fact remains that employee commitment is a critical factor in the success of any organization. Committed employees are more likely to be productive, innovative and satisfied with their job only when their job meet their needs. In public schools in Rivers State employee turnover is a significant concern that impact the quality of education. A clear understanding of the factors that influence teachers decisions to stay or leave is crucial for school administrators to implement strategies to positive and supportive work environment. Organization investing in employee well- being, providing adequate compensation and benefits, and offering opportunities for professional growth, schools can enhance teachers retention and improve the overall quality of education in line with global best practices.

However, there are key factors influencing employee turnover in a contemporary school system.

Compensation and benefits:

- **Insufficient in salary payments:** Poor salaries compared to other professions can lead to dissatisfaction and turnover
- **Deferments salary payments:** Irregular and delay in payment of salary can weaken morale and loyalty.
- **Limited Benefits:** Lack of adequate benefits, such as good retirement plans or package, and health insurance can adversely affects their job or satisfaction at work place.

Working Conditions:

- **Excessive workload:** Heavy work load and long working hours can lead to break down and diminished job satisfaction.
- **Poor Facilities:** Insufficient classroom, lack of instructional aids, and poor maintenance culture can create a stressful working environment.
- **Big class size:** Overcrowded classrooms can impede effective instructional service delivery, leading to employee frustration.

Job discontentment:

- Lack of Recognition and Appreciation.
- Lack of recognition and appreciation for employees job well done can demotivate teachers.
- Limited opportunities for staff professional development program
- Lack of opportunities for training and development of teachers can deter growth and development.
- Incompetent leadership: ineffective leadership, lack of support can create an unfavorable work environment.
- Conversely, there are factors also that is influencing employee retention to take ownership of their job.

Competitive Compensation and Benefits

Fair Salaries: Prompt and adequate payments of salary can boost morale and job satisfaction of an employee at work place.

Comprehensive Benefits Packages: Offering attractive benefits, such as health insurance, pension plans, and housing allowances, can enhance employee retention.

Good Work Environment:

Supportive Leadership: Effective leadership, characterized by trust, respect, and open communication, can create a positive work culture.

Downsized Workload: Implementing strategies to reduce workload and improve work-life balance can enhance employee job satisfaction.

Professional Development Opportunities: Providing opportunities for training, workshops, and conferences can motivate teachers and boost their skills.

Recognition and Rewards:

Public Recognition: Acknowledging and recognizing teachers' contributions through awards, certificates, or public praise can boost morale.

Performance-Based Incentives: Implementing performance-based incentives, such as bonuses or promotions, can motivate teachers to excel.

Job Security and Career Advancement:

Clear Career Paths: Providing clear career paths and opportunities for advancement can motivate teachers to stay.

Job Security: Ensuring job security and avoiding arbitrary dismissals can enhance employee loyalty.

In the light of this background, this study investigated impact of employee commitment as a tool for enhancing productivity in management of school service delivery in Obio- Akpor local government area of Rivers State

Theoretical framework

The affective commitment theory was used for this study, propounded by John Meyer and Natalie Allen in 1991. The theory suggests that employee are more likely to be committed when they emotionally identify with organizations goals and value. It emphasizes the role of positive emotions, trust, and identification with organizations value fostering commitment.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was descriptive survey design. The population comprised 1,250 teachers in public senior secondary school in Obio/ Akpor Local Government of Rivers State (source: planning Research and Statistics, department, RSSB, Port Harcourt Rivers State 2023).The sample size of the study was 375 teachers. Stratified random sampling was used to select 375 teachers which represents 30% of the population.A questionnaire titled: Impact of Employee Commitment as a tool for Enhancing Productivity in Management of School Service Delivery Questionnaire (IECTEPMSSDQ) was used for data collection. The instrument was self- designed structured questionnaire on a four point modified likert scale of strongly agreed (SA) 4, Agreed (A) 3, Disagreed (DA) 2, strongly disagreed (SD) 1. Section A of the instrument was made of information on demographics variable of the respondent, while section B comprised items designed to obtain answers to research question for the study. The reliability of the instrument method was determined through

Cronbach alpha reliability statistics which gave reliability index of 0.88. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *In what ways can employees commitment enhanced productivity in management of service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Table1: Mean and Standard deviation on the ways employees commitment can enhanced productivity in management of school service delivery

s/n	ways can employees commitment enhanced productivity in management of service delivery	257 male staff		118 female staff		Mean set	Decision
			Std		Std		
1	Effective leadership style that reward hardwork	3.29	.60	2.63	.48	2.96	Agreed
2	Delegation of authority and responsibility to staff members	3.23	.48	2.75	.75	2.99	Agreed
3	Networking and collaboration	3.33	.53	3.13	.85	3.23	Agreed
4	Empowering employees to make decisions about their job	3.36	.56	2.81	.73	3.09	Agreed
5	Creating a supportive work environment for all staff	3.25	.46	3.43	.72	3.34	Agreed
6	Paying bonuses to workers that are diligent	3.19	.48	2.56	.92	2.88	Agreed
	Cluster mean	3.28	0.52	2.89	0.74	3.08	Agreed

Data on table 1 showed that items with serial numbers 1 to 6 have their various of 2.96, 2.99, 3.23, 3.09, 3.34 and 2.88 are above the criterion mean value of 2.50 and were agreed by male and female staff as the ways employees' commitment can enhance productivity in management of service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The various ways employees' commitment can enhance productivity in management of service delivery are through effective leadership style that reward hardwork, delegation of authority and responsibility to staff members, networking and collaboration, empowering employees to make decisions about their job, creating a supportive work environment for all staff and paying bonuses to workers that are diligent.

Research Question 2 : *In what ways can delegation of authority and responsibility by principal enhance employee commitment in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Area of Rivers of State?.*

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation on the ways delegation of authority and responsibility by principal can enhance employee commitment in management of school service delivery

s/n	ways can delegation of authority and responsibility by principal enhance employee commitment in management of school service delivery	257 male staff		118 female staff	Mean set	Decision	
			Std				
7	Empowering employees to develop skills and abilities	3.19	.52	3.23	.71	3.21	Agreed
8	Giving employees a sense of ownership and responsibility of their duties	3.32	.47	2.68	.90	3.00	Agreed
9	Improving communication between leadership and workers	3.39	.49	3.04	.87	3.22	Agreed
10	Increasing employee productivity in the service delivery	3.42	.49	3.11	.75	3.27	Agreed
11	Delegation empowers teachers to put their ideas to work	3.57	.49	2.64	.78	3.11	Agreed
12	Delegation enables principal to focus his/her attention to more pressing administrative matters	3.28	.45	2.66	.64	2.97	Agreed
	Cluster mean	3.36	0.49	2.89	0.78	3.13	Agreed

Data on table 2 showed that items with serial numbers 7 to 12 have their various of 3.21, 3.00, 3.22, 3.27, 3.11 and 2.97 are above the criterion mean value of 2.50 and were agreed by male and female staff as the ways delegation of authority and responsibility by principal can enhance employee commitment in management of school service delivery. The various ways delegation of authority and responsibility by principal can enhance employee commitment in management of school service delivery through

Empowering employees to develop skills and abilities, Giving employees a sense of ownership and responsibility of their duties, Improving communication between leadership and workers, Increasing employee productivity in the service delivery, Delegation empowers teachers to put their ideas to work and Delegation enables principal to focus his/her attention to more pressing administrative matters.

Hypothesis1: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female staff on how employee commitment can enhanced productivity in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table3: z-test of the mean difference between male and female staff on how employee commitments can enhance productivity in management of school service delivery

Gender	n	Std	df	z-cal.	Sig.	Alpha value	Decision
Male principals	257	19.66	2.24				
Female principals	118	17.31	3.16	373	8.23	0.00	0.05

Data on table 3 revealed that male staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 19.66 and 2.24 while female staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 17.31 and 3.16 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 373 and z-value of 8.23, the hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female staff on how employee commitment can enhanced productivity in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female staff on how delegation of authority and responsibility by principal can enhance employees commitment in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table4: z-test of mean difference between male and female staff on how delegation of authority and responsibility by the principal can enhance demployee commitment in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Rivers State.

Gender	n	Std	df	z-cal.	Sig.	Alpha value	Decision
Male principals	257	20.18	2.16				
Female principals	118	17.36	3.75	373	9.22	0.00	0.05

Data on table 4 revealed that male staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 20.18 and 2.16 while female staff have mean and standard deviation scores of 17.36 and 3.75 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 373 and z-value of 9.22, the hypothesis is rejected because the significant value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05. Therefore there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female staff on how delegation of authority and responsibility by principal can enhance employees commitment in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

The findings of this study are that:

1. The various ways employees’ commitment can enhance productivity in management of service delivery are through effective leadership style that reward hardwork, delegation of authority and responsibility to staff members, networking and collaboration, empowering employees to make decisions about their job, creating a supportive work environment for all staff and paying bonuses to workers that are diligent. The hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female staff on how employee commitment can enhanced productivity in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. The various ways delegation of authority and responsibility by principal can enhance employee commitment in management of school service delivery through Empowering employees to develop skills

and abilities, Giving employees a sense of ownership and responsibility of their duties, Improving communication between leadership and workers, Increasing employee productivity in the service delivery, Delegation empowers teachers to put their ideas to work and Delegation enables principal to focus his/her attention to more pressing administrative matters. The hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference between the mean rating of male and female staff on how delegation of authority and responsibility by principal can enhance employees commitment in management of school service delivery in public senior secondary school in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

CONCLUSION

In particular, from the proceeding of pages it was established that investing in employee to be committed is not just an ethical imperative, but also a strategic investment in a school success. Having established from the proceeding of pages the ways employee commitment and authority and responsibility by the principal can be an effective tool to increase teachers' commitment level and raising productivity of school, it become imperative to note that the work an employees does can only be productive when he or she have zero tolerance and committed to it. Every employee feels happy and are willing to put in their best, and take the organization they belong to an enviable standard when they see their presence valued and recognized. Hence, school administrators should learn to avoid anything that will demoralized teachers in the course of performing their statutory duties. This is because the level of success recorded in the educational system in any country is attributed to teachers level of commitment.

RECOMMENDATION

Government as a matter of urgency should promotes teachers as when due, this will increase their commitments level at work place

School principal should always involve teachers in decision making process, this will enable them to bring in their best because they feel the organization they belong recognizes their presence.

Awards and gift item should be given to teachers who are committed with their work, this will make others teachers to sit up with their job.

Teachers who fail to comply with their assign task in school, should be disciplined immediately, that we make other to be mindful of what they do and as well make other to be committed with their job.

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